

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 40:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 40:1 לְמִנְצֵחַ לְדָוִד</p>
<p>Psa. 40:1 I ^awaited ¹patiently for the LORD; And He inclined to me and ^bheard my cry. ² He brought me up out of the ^apit of destruction, out of the ¹miry clay, And ^bHe set my feet upon a rock ^cmaking my footsteps firm. ³ He put a ^anew song in my mouth, a song of praise to our God; Many will ^bsee and fear And will trust in the LORD.</p>	<p>מִזְמוֹר : ² קָנִיָּה קָנִיתִי יְהוָה וַיֵּט אֵלַי וַיִּשְׁמַע שׁוֹעֲתִי : ³ וַיַּעֲלֵנִי אֶמְבֹּר שָׁאוֹן מִטְּיֵט הַתְּהוֹן וַיִּקֶּם עַל-סִלְע רַגְלִי כוֹנֵן אֲשֶׁרִי : ⁴ וַיִּתֵּן בְּפִי אֵשֶׁר חָדַשׁ תְּהִלָּה לְאֱלֹהֵינוּ יִרְאוּ רַבִּים וַיִּירְאוּ וַיִּבְטְחוּ בִיהוָה : ⁵ אֲשֶׁרִי הַגִּבֹּר</p>
<p>Psa. 40:4 How ^ablessed is the man who has made the LORD his trust, And ^bhas not ¹turned to the proud, nor to those who ¹lapse into falsehood. ⁵ Many, O LORD my God, are ^athe wonders which You have done, And Your ^bthoughts toward us; There is none to compare with You. If I would declare and speak of them, They ^cwould be too numerous to count.</p>	<p>אֲשֶׁר-שָׁם יְהוָה מִבְּטְחוֹ וְלֹא-פָנָה אֶל-רְחֹבִים וְשֹׁטֵי כָזָב : ⁶ רַבּוֹת עָשִׂיתָ אֶתָּה יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי נִפְלְאוֹתֶיךָ וּמַחֲשַׁבְתֶּיךָ אֵלֵינוּ אֵין אַרְךְ אֱלֹהֵיךָ אַנְיָדָה וְאַדְבָּרָה עֲצָמוֹ מִסֶּפֶר : ⁷ זָבַח וּמִנְחָה לֹא-חִפְצָתָ אֲזִנִּים כָּרִיתָ לִּי עוֹלָה וַחֲטָאָה לֹא שָׁאֲלָתָ : ⁸ אֲזִ אָמַרְתִּי הִנֵּה-בָאתִי בְּמִגְלַת-סֶפֶר כָּתוּב עָלַי : ⁹</p>
<p>Psa. 40:6 ^{1a}Sacrifice and meal offering You have not desired; My ears You have ²opened; Burnt offering and sin offering You have not required. ⁷ Then I said, “Behold, I come;</p>	<p>אֲשֶׁר-שָׁם יְהוָה מִבְּטְחוֹ וְלֹא-פָנָה אֶל-רְחֹבִים וְשֹׁטֵי כָזָב : ⁶ רַבּוֹת עָשִׂיתָ אֶתָּה יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵי נִפְלְאוֹתֶיךָ וּמַחֲשַׁבְתֶּיךָ אֵלֵינוּ אֵין אַרְךְ אֱלֹהֵיךָ אַנְיָדָה וְאַדְבָּרָה עֲצָמוֹ מִסֶּפֶר : ⁷ זָבַח וּמִנְחָה לֹא-חִפְצָתָ אֲזִנִּים כָּרִיתָ לִּי עוֹלָה וַחֲטָאָה לֹא שָׁאֲלָתָ : ⁸ אֲזִ אָמַרְתִּי הִנֵּה-בָאתִי בְּמִגְלַת-סֶפֶר כָּתוּב עָלַי : ⁹</p>

In the scroll of the book it is
¹written of me.

⁸ "I delight to do Your will, O my
God;

^bYour Law is within my heart."

Psa. 40:9 I have "proclaimed glad
tidings of righteousness in the great
congregation;

Behold, I will ^bnot restrain my lips,
O LORD, "You know.

¹⁰ I have "not hidden Your
righteousness within my heart;

I have ^bspoken of Your
faithfulness and Your salvation;

I have not concealed Your
lovingkindness and Your truth from the
great congregation.

Psa. 40:11 You, O LORD, will not
withhold Your compassion from me;

¹Your "lovingkindness and Your
truth will continually preserve me.

¹² For evils beyond number have
"surrounded me;

My ^biniquities have overtaken me,
so that I am not able to see;

They are "more numerous than the
hairs of my head,

And my ^aheart has ¹failed me.

Psa. 40:13 "Be pleased, O LORD, to
deliver me;

Make ^bhaste, O LORD, to help me.

¹⁴ Let those be "ashamed and
humiliated together

Who ^bseek my ¹life to destroy it;

Let those be turned back and
dishonored

Who delight ²in my hurt.

לַעֲשׂוֹת־רְצוֹנֶךָ אֱלֹהֵי

חַבְצֵלְתִי וְתוֹרַתְךָ בְּתוֹךְ מִעֵי :

¹⁰ בְּשִׁרְתִּי צְדָק אֶבְקֶה לְרַב

הַנְּהַל שִׁפְתֵי לֹא אֶכְלָא יְהוָה

אֶתְּהָ יַדְעָתָ : ¹¹ צְדָקַתְךָ לֹא-

כְּסִיתִי אֶבְתּוֹךְ לְבִי אֶמְוִנְתֶּךָ

וְתִשׁוּעָתְךָ אֶמְרֵתִי לֹא-

כְּתִרְתִּי תִסְדֶּךָ וְאֶמְתֶּךָ

לְקַהֵל רַב : ¹² אֶתְּהָ יְהוָה

לֹא־תִכְלָא רַחֲמֶיךָ מִמְּנִי

תִסְדֶּךָ וְאֶמְתֶּךָ תִמְיֵד

יִצְרוּנִי : ¹³ כִּי אֶפְפוּ־עָלַי |

רָעוֹת עַד־אֵין מִסְפָּר

הַשִּׁיגוּנִי עֲזוֹנְתִי וְלֹא־יִכְלְתִי

לְרֹאוֹת עֲצָמוֹ מִשְׁעֲרוֹת

רֹאשִׁי וְלִבִּי עֲזָבוּנִי : ¹⁴ רַצְנָה

יְהוָה לְהַצִּילֵנִי יְהוָה

לְעֲזָרְתִי תוֹשָׁה : ¹⁵ יִבְשׁוּ

וַיִּחַפְּרוּ וַיִּתְחַדּוּ מִבְּקִשֵׁי נַפְשִׁי

לְסַפּוֹתֶיהָ יִסְגּוּ אַחֲזוֹר וַיִּכְלְמוּ

חַבְצֵי רַעְתִּי : ¹⁶ יִשְׁמוּ עַל־

עַקֵּב בְּשִׁפְתָם הָאֹמְרִים לִי

<p>¹⁵ Let those ^abe ¹appalled because of their shame Who ^bsay to me, “Aha, aha!”</p> <p>¹⁶ ^aLet all who seek You rejoice and be glad in You; Let those who love Your salvation ^bsay continually, “The LORD be magnified!”</p> <p>¹⁷ Since ^aI am afflicted and needy, ^{1b}Let the Lord be mindful of me. You are my help and my deliverer; Do not delay, O my God.</p>	<p>הָאֵתָה אֶהְאֵת : ¹⁷ וְשִׁישׁוּ וְיִשְׂמְחוּ אֶבְרָךְ כָּל-מִבְּקֹשִׁיךְ יֹאמְרוּ תָמִיד יִגְדַּל יְהוָה אֱהַבִי תְשׁוּעָתְךָ : ¹⁸ וְאָנֹכִי עָנִי וְאֶבְיוֹן אֲדַנִּי יִתְשָׁב לִי עֲזַרְתִּי וּמִפְּלִטִי אֶתָּה אֱלֹהֵי אֵל-תְּאַחֵר :</p>
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References

<p>Psalm 40:1 ¹Or <i>intently</i> ^aPs 25:5; 27:14; 37:7 ^bPs 34:15</p> <p>Psalm 40:2 ¹Lit <i>mud of the mire</i> ^aPs 69:2, 14; Jer 38:6 ^bPs 27:5 ^cPs 37:23</p> <p>Psalm 40:3 ^aPs 32:7; 33:3 ^bPs 52:6; 64:9</p> <p>Psalm 40:4 ¹Lit <i>regard</i> ^aPs 34:8; 84:12 ^bJob 37:24 ^cPs 125:5</p> <p>Psalm 40:5 ^aJob 5:9; Ps 136:4 ^bPs 139:17; Is 55:8 ^cPs 71:15; 139:18</p> <p>Psalm 40:6 ¹i.e. Blood sacrifice ²Lit <i>dug</i>; or possibly <i>pierced</i> ^a1 Sam 15:22; Ps 51:16; Is 1:11; Jer 6:20; 7:22, 23; Amos 5:22; Mic 6:6-8; Heb 10:5-7</p> <p>Psalm 40:7 ¹Or <i>prescribed for</i></p> <p>Psalm 40:8 ^aJohn 4:34 ^bPs 37:31; Jer 31:33; 2 Cor 3:3</p>	<p>Psalm 40:9 ^aPs 22:22, 25 ^bPs 119:13 ^cJosh 22:22; Ps 139:4</p> <p>Psalm 40:10 ^aActs 20:20, 27 ^bPs 89:1</p> <p>Psalm 40:11 ¹Or <i>May...preserve</i> ^aPs 43:3; 57:3; 61:7; Prov 20:28</p> <p>Psalm 40:12 ¹Lit <i>forsaken</i> ^aPs 18:5; 116:3 ^bPs 38:4; 65:3 ^cPs 69:4 ^dPs 73:26</p> <p>Psalm 40:13 ^aPs 70:1 ^bPs 22:19; 71:12</p> <p>Psalm 40:14 ¹Or <i>soul</i> ²Or <i>to injure me</i> ^aPs 35:4, 26; 70:2; 71:13 ^bPs 63:9</p>
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Psalm 40:15

¹Or *desolated*

^aPs 70:3

^bPs 35:21; 70:3

Psalm 40:16

^aPs 70:4

^bPs 35:27

Psalm 40:17

¹Or *The Lord is mindful*

^aPs 70:5; 86:1; 109:22

^bPs 40:5; 1 Pet 5:7

Targum

Psa. 40:1 For praise. Of David, a psalm. ² I truly hoped in the LORD, and he turned to me and received my supplication. ³ And he brought me up from the pit of turmoil, from the mire of filth; and he set my feet on the rock, he made my steps firm. ⁴ And he put in my mouth a new psalm: Let there be praise before the LORD our God, let many see and fear and hope in the word of the LORD. ⁵ Happy the man who made the LORD his confidence, and did not look toward the disobedient and those who speak falsehood. ⁶ Many are the miracles that you have done, O LORD my God; your wonders and favor towards us are impossible to set out; I will recount and speak to you your praise; they are too great to tell. ⁷ You do not want sacrifice and offering; you have scooped out ears for me to hear your redemption; you have not asked for holocaust and sin offering. ⁸ Then I said, “Behold, I have entered into eternal life,” whenever I occupy myself with the scroll of the book of Torah that was written for my sake. ⁹ I desire to do your will, O God; and your Torah is contained in my deepest self. ¹⁰ I have proclaimed righteousness in the great assembly; behold, I will not withhold my lips; O LORD my God, you know [this]. ¹¹ I have not concealed your righteousness in my heart, I have uttered your truth and your redemption; I have not kept back your goodness and faithfulness in the great assembly. ¹² Therefore, you, O LORD, do not withhold your mercy from me; may your goodness and truth always keep me. ¹³ For evils are strong against me, until they are without number; my sins have overtaken me and I cannot see; they are more numerous than the hairs of my head; and my thoughts have left me. ¹⁴ Be pleased, O LORD, to save me; O LORD, hasten to my aid. ¹⁵ Those who seek to destroy my soul will be ashamed and confused together; those who desire my ruin will turn back and be disgraced. ¹⁶ They will become senseless because of their shame – those who say to me, “We have rejoiced at his ruin, we rejoiced at his misery.” ¹⁷ All who seek you will rejoice and be glad in your word; and those who love your

redemption will say continually, “Let the might of the LORD be magnified.” ¹⁸ But I am humble and poor, O LORD; let good be devised for me, you are my help and salvation; O my God, do not delay.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

The first eleven verses of this Psalm is a joyous song that David composed when he returned to full health. In the latter part of the Psalm, David speaks about the many dangers that were confronting him.

Superscript

מְנַצֵּחַ (meNatzecha) – means victory. This word is the name of the eighth Sefirah of the Tree of Life. It is not translated in the NASB translation. David called upon the Sefirah Netzach to bring him victory over his enemies. David felt that when he was successful, the LORD was being honored.

To the Sefirah Netzah. A Psalm of David.

Verse one

David hoped for the LORD in the past to help him, and He always did.

I have often hoped for the LORD in the past, striving for Him, and He inclined to hear my cry.

Verse two

שׁוֹן (shaon) – means “destruction.” This word also denotes a spiritual desolation or spiritual abandonment. David said that the LORD brought him out of his spiritual aloneness.

He raised me up from my spiritual desolation, from the miry mud; He has set my feet upon a rock and firmly established my steps.

Verse three

Since the LORD rose David from his spiritual isolation he wanted to sing a new glorious song to the LORD.

**He put a new song in my mouth, a praise to the LORD almighty acts.
Many will see and show reverence, and at the same time, learn to trust in the LORD.**

Verse four

No matter your situation, King David reminds us always to trust that the LORD is there and will help. All you have to do is ask and have faith.

Forward strides that man who has made when the LORD is the fount of his trust, and has not turned to the arrogant, nor to those who turn away in faithlessness and deceit.

Verse five

David acknowledges the wonderful things that the LORD has done in the Universe.

Many, O LORD my God, are the wonders which You have done, and Your thoughts toward us; There is none to compare with You. If I would declare and speak of them, They would be too numerous to count.

Verse six

The LORD is not looking for sacrifices from those who believed in Him. He is looking for loyal obedience to the Word and a greater sense of duty toward Him. Sacrifices are usually made when a person sins. The LORD is not interested in sin; therefore, the sacrifices are not desired. In other words, do not sin!

You did not desire a meal-offering and sacrifice. You have pierced my ears, You have surely not required ascent-offerings.

Verse seven

David understood that he needed to express his gratitude to the LORD in writing.

So, having contemplated all this, I said: I have come with a written scroll of a book upon me. I understand that I need to express my gratitude with words, both spoken and written.

Verse eight

David said that he was to abandon all his personal desires and accept the Torah in his heart.

To fulfill Your will, my LORD, was my desire, and I accept Your doctrine in my innermost parts.

Verse nine

David immersed himself in the Torah. He came to appreciate it and understand it. He then sought to bring other people to the Torah. He believed that he was obliged to bring the Torah to the people.

I proclaimed righteousness in the great congregation; behold, I shall also not close my lips in the future, O LORD. You know this.

Verse ten

When David proclaimed the destiny of humanity in gatherings, he never concealed what the LORD had done for him. David was guided through the LORD's faithfulness to David and David's faith in the LORD.

I have not hidden Your righteousness within my heart; I have spoken of Your faithfulness and Your salvation; I have not concealed Your lovingkindness and Your truth from the great congregation.

Verse eleven and twelve

The LORD preserved David even when he sinned. Through the Sefirah Chesed, David was forgiven for his sin, and the LORD shined love upon him.

You, O LORD, allowed the Sefirah Chesed to shine upon me. Chesed's love preserved me.

For innumerable evils have beset me once more; my iniquities have overtaken me, and I was no longer able to see; they were more numerous than the hairs on my head, and my heart has failed me.

Verse thirteen to fifteen

David turned to the LORD seeking help because of the sins of the flesh. He prayed for the LORD to deliver him. He also hoped for his enemies to come to know the LORD.

Be pleased, O LORD, to deliver me; Make haste, O LORD, to help me.

Let those be ashamed and humiliated together who seek my ¹life to destroy it; Let those be turned back and dishonored who delight in my hurt.

Let those be appalled because of their shame. Who say to me, "Aha, aha!"

Verse Sixteen

Nothing is as glorious as the LORD. The people who realize that the hand of the LORD is in historical events will receive salvation.

Let all who seek You rejoice and be glad in You; Let those who love Your salvation say continually, “the LORD be magnified!”

Verse seventeen

David acknowledged that he will always need the LORD’s help.

Since I am afflicted and needy, let the Lord be mindful of me. You are my help and my deliverer; Do not delay, O my God.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzah. A Psalm of David.

I have often hoped for the LORD in the past, striving for Him, and He inclined to hear my cry.

He raised me up from my spiritual desolation, from the miry mud; He has set my feet upon a rock and firmly established my steps.

He put a new song in my mouth, a praise to the LORD almighty acts. Many will see and show reverence, and at the same time, learn to trust in the LORD.

Forward strides that man who has made when the LORD is the fount of his trust, and has not turned to the arrogant, nor to those who turn away in faithlessness and deceit.

Many, O LORD my God, are the wonders which You have done, and Your thoughts toward us; There is none to compare with You. If I would declare and speak of them, They would be too numerous to count.

You did not desire a meal-offering and sacrifice. You have pierced my ears, You have surely not required ascent-offerings.

So, having contemplated all this, I said: I have come with a written scroll of a book upon me. I understand that I need to express my gratitude with words, both spoken and written.

To fulfill Your will, my LORD, was my desire, and I accept Your doctrine in my innermost parts.

I proclaimed righteousness in the great congregation; behold, I shall also not close my lips in the future, O LORD. You know this.

I have not hidden Your righteousness within my heart; I have spoken of Your faithfulness and Your salvation; I have not concealed Your lovingkindness and Your truth from the great congregation.

You, O LORD, allowed the Sefirah Chesed to shine upon me. Chesed's love preserved me.

For innumerable evils have beset me once more; my iniquities have overtaken me, and I was no longer able to see; they were more numerous than the hairs on my head, and my heart has failed me.

Be pleased, O LORD, to deliver me; Make haste, O LORD, to help me.

Let those be ashamed and humiliated together who seek my ¹life to destroy it; Let those be turned back and dishonored who delight in my hurt.

Let those be appalled because of their shame. Who say to me, "Aha, aha!"

Let all who seek You rejoice and be glad in You; Let those who love Your salvation say continually, "the LORD be magnified!"

Since I am afflicted and needy, let the Lord be mindful of me. You are my help and my deliverer; Do not delay, O my God.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

